

A STUDY OF EMOTIONAL MATURITY OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN NORTH BENGAL

Samten Tamang

*M.A. (Education), Department of Education,
Visva Bharati (Santiniketan)*

Abstract:

Emotional maturity is a process in which the personality is continuously striving for greater sense of emotional health, both intra-psychically and intra-personality. The characteristics of an emotionally mature are hetero-sexuality, appreciation of attitude and behavior of others, tendency to adopt the attitudes and habits of others and capacity to delay his own responses. Therefore, the emotionally mature is not one who necessarily has resolved all conditions that aroused anxiety and hostility but it is continuously in process of seeing himself in clear perspective, continually involved in a struggle to gain healthy integration of feeling, thinking action. The objective of the study was to study the emotional maturity of higher secondary school students in relation to gender and type of family variation in total and component wise variations. Normative survey method was adopted. A sample of 100 students from 4 schools of Darjeeling, North Bengal was selected by simple random sampling procedure. Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS-SB) developed by Singh and Bharagava (2005) was used for data collection. Findings of the study were that most of the students are emotionally immature and there is difference in emotional maturity in terms of type of family variation.

Samten Tamang:- A STUDY OF EMOTIONAL MATURITY OF Senior Secondary

Key words: Emotional maturity, Emotional stability, Emotional independence

Introduction:

Emotional maturity is defined as, “A process in which the personality is continually striving for greater sense of emotional health, both intra-psychically and intra-personally”. In brief emotional maturity can be called as the process of impulse control through the agency of “self” or "ego". Emotional maturity is not only the effective determinant of personality pattern but it also helps to control the growth of adolescent’s development. The concept “Mature” emotional behavior of any level is that which reflects the fruits of normal emotional development. A person who is able to keep his emotions under control i.e., able to break delay and to suffer without self-pity, might still be emotionally stunned and childish. Morgan (1934) stated the view that an adequate theory of emotional maturity must take account of the full scope of the individuality, power and his ability to enjoy the use of his powers.

Components of emotional maturity:

a. Emotional Stability: It refers to the characteristics of a person that does not allow him to react excessively or given to swings in mood or marked changes in any emotive situation. The emotionally stable person is able to do what is required of him in any given situation.

b. Emotional Progression: It refers to a feeling of adequate advancement and growing vitality of emotions in relation to the environment to ensure a positive thinking imbued with righteousness and contentment.

c. Social Adjustment: It refers to a process of interaction between the needs of a person and demands of the social environment in any given situation, so that they can maintain and adapt a desired relationship with environment.

d. **Personality Integration:** It is the process of unifying the diverse elements of an individual's motives and dynamic tendencies, resulting in harmonious coactions and de-escalation of the inner conflict in the undaunted expression of behavior.

e. **Independence:** It is the capacity of a person's attitudinal tendency to be self reliant or of resistance to control by others, where he can take his decisions by his own judgment based on facts by utilizing his intellectual and creative potentialities.

Kaplan and Baron elaborate the characteristics of an emotionally mature person; say that he has the capacity to withstand delay in satisfaction of needs. He has the ability to tolerate a reasonable amount of frustration. He has belief in long-term planning and is capable of delaying or revising his expectations in terms of demands of situations. An emotionally mature child has the capacity to make effective adjustment with himself, members of his family his peers in the school, society and culture. But maturity means not merely the capacity for such attitude and functioning but also the ability to enjoy them fully. The most outstanding mark of emotional maturity is ability to bear tension. Other marks are an indifference toward certain kinds of stimuli that affect the adolescent and he develops moodiness and sentimentally. Besides, emotionally matured person persists the capacity for fun and recreation. He enjoys both play and responsibility activities and keep them in proper balance.

Jadhav (2010) conducted a research on the relationship between home environment and emotional maturity among college going students of Belgaum District in Karnataka and it was found that, there was no positive and significant relationship between home environment and emotional maturity among the urban students, studying in government colleges, with high socio-economic status and students less than 20 years of age. Subbarayan (2011) intended to measure the emotional maturity of students. The result of the study showed that the emotional maturity of college students was extremely unstable. It was also found that the sex, community and the family type did not play any role in the emotional maturity of the college students. Mahmoudi (2012) conducted a study to see the Emotional maturity and adjustment level of students and stated that high positive

correlation was obtained between emotional maturity and overall adjustment. Aashra (2013) studied influence of emotional maturity and self-actualization in graduate and post-graduate students and found that there was significant difference in emotional maturity among graduate and post-graduate students. There was significant difference in self-actualization among graduate and post-graduate students. Sinha (2014) studied the relationship between emotional maturity and adjustment of college students to see the impact of gender on emotional maturity and adjustment. The result revealed that there were significant differences between boys and girls students in term of their emotional maturity and adjustment viewpoint.

Rationale of the study:

In the present circumstances, youth as well as children are facing difficulties in life. These difficulties are giving rise to many psycho-somatic problems such as anxiety, tensions, frustrations and emotional upsets in day to day life. So the study of emotional life is now emerging as a descriptive science, comparable with anatomy. It deals with interplay of forces with intensities and quantities. Available tests are crude and measure chiefly the degree of dependence. But this test measures the different aspects of emotional maturity. The specific needs for identifying these phenomena of Emotional Maturity as a natural and inevitable essential outcome of student growth and development rather than among pathological symptom. The Emotional maturity becomes important in the behavior of individuals. As the students are the pillars of the future generations their value pattern of Emotional Maturity are vital. So the present study intends to measure the Emotional Maturity of higher secondary school students.

While doing the research, the researcher tried to answer the following queries.

- Are the students emotionally stable in relation to gender and type of family variation?
- Are the students emotionally progressed in relation to gender and type of family variation?
- Are the students socially adjusted in relation to gender and type of family variation?
- Do the students have personality integration in relation to gender and type of family variation?

- Are the students independent in relation to gender and type of family variation?

Therefore, the problem is stated as “A Study of Emotional Maturity of Senior Secondary School Students in North Bengal”.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the emotional stability of students in relation to gender and type of family variation.
- To study the emotional progression of students in relation to gender and type of family variation.
- To study the social adjustment of students in relation to gender and type of family variation.
- To study the personality integration of students in relation to gender and type of family variation.
- To study the independence of students in relation to gender and type of family variation.

Hypothesis of the Study:

The null hypotheses for the research topic are as follows:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the emotional stability of students in relation to gender variation.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the emotional stability of students in relation to type of family variation.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the emotional progression of students in relation to gender variation.

Ho₄: There is no significant difference in the emotional progression of students in relation to type of family variation.

Ho₅: There is no significant difference in the social adjustment of students in relation to gender variation.

Ho₆: There is no significant difference in the social adjustment of students in relation to type of family variation.

Ho₇: There is no significant difference in the personality integration of students in relation to gender variation.

Ho₈: There is no significant difference in the personality integration of students in relation to type of family variation.

Ho₉: There is no significant difference in the independence of students in relation to gender variation.

Ho₁₀: There is no significant difference in the independence of students in relation to type of family variation.

Methodology:

The Design: Normative survey method was adopted in the present research to obtain pertinent information concerning the area of the study. Hence, this method of ex-post facto type in nature and content was used in this study.

Sample: A sample of 100 students from 4 schools of Darjeeling, North Bengal was selected by simple random sampling procedure.

Tools used for the Study: Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS-SB) developed by Singh and Bharagava (2005) was used for data collection. It consists of 48 items including several aspects of problems or issue related to emotional maturity.

Analysis and Interpretation of data: Hypotheses testing

Under this subsection attempts were made by the investigator to interpret the data in terms of the objectives and hypotheses formulated earlier. For this the sample was split into two sub-samples namely: Boy Vs Girl and Nuclear Vs Joint Family, In order to make a statistical comparison the 't' ratios were calculated in all the cases and the results were presented in each and every cases.

For determining the significance of difference between the means and variances of each of the contrasts the 't' ratios were calculated and tested for significance at 0.05 level and 0.01 level of significance and depending upon the result, the hypotheses were rejected or accepted. The corroboration of earlier studies was made with regard to the result and interpretation was made accordingly. The details of this were presented below.

Analysis of Emotional Maturity of Students in Relation to Gender Variation (In Total)

In order to test to test the gender difference in emotional maturity (in total) of students 't' ratio had been calculated and presented below:

Table 1: Test of significance of difference on Emotional Maturity of students (in total) due to gender variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	't'	Remark
Gender	Boy	50	109.46	30.36	5.98	1.18	NS
	Girl	50	116.56	29.45			

P values of t at 0.05 level= 1.98, 0.01 level= 2.63 for df 98, NS refers to Not Significant

It was quite evident from the above table that the obtained value of 't' ratio was 1.18 which was smaller than the table value 0.05 level= 1.98, 0.01 level= 2.63. Hence the 't' ratio (1.18) in case of gender variation was not significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level and we may concluded that there was no significant difference between boy and girl in their emotional maturity. The result was in the conformity with the earlier studies done by Sivakumar (2010) who found there is no significant difference between boys and girls on emotional maturity.

Analysis of Emotional Maturity of Students in Relation to Type of Family Variation (Total)

In order to test to test the type of family difference in emotional maturity (total) of students ‘t’ ratio had been calculated and presented below:

Table 2: Test of significance of difference on Emotional Maturity of students (total) due to type of family variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	‘t’	Remark
Type of family	Nuclear	50	116.52	31.04	5.98	1.17	NS
	Joint	50	109.5	28.75			

It was quite evident from the above table that the obtained value of ‘t’ ratio was 1.17 which was smaller than the table value 0.05 level= 1.98, 0.01 level= 2.63. Hence the ‘t’ ratio (1.17) in case of type of family variation was not significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level and we may concluded that there was no significant difference in their emotional maturity due to type of family difference. The result was in the conformity with the earlier studies done by John Louis and Doss (2007) who found that there does not exist any difference due to type of family variation.

Analysis of Emotional Stability of Students in Relation to Gender Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the Emotional Stability of students in relation to gender variation. For this the null hypothesis H_{01} was formulated as follows, “There will be no significant difference in the emotional stability of students in relation to gender variation”. In order to test the gender difference in emotional stability of students ‘t’ ratio had been calculated and presented below:

Table 3: Test of significance of difference on Emotional Stability of students due to gender variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	't'	Remark
Gender	Boy	50	23.38	7.58	1.51	1.35	NS
	Girl	50	25.42	7.50			

It was quite evident from the above table that the obtained value of 't' ratio was 1.35 which was smaller than the table value 0.05 level= 1.98, 0.01 level= 2.63. Hence the 't' ratio (1.35) in case of gender variation was not significant at 0.05 and 0.01 level. So the null hypothesis Ho₁ could not be rejected and concluded that there was no significant difference between boy and girl in their emotional stability.

Analysis of Emotional Stability of Students in Relation to type of family Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the Emotional Stability of students in relation to type of family variation. For this the null hypothesis Ho₂ was formulated as follows "There will be no significant difference in the emotional stability of students in relation to type of family variation". For the appropriateness of the study, 't' ratio was calculated as shown in the following table.

Table 4: Test of significance of difference on Emotional Stability of students due to type of family variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	't'	Remark
Type of Family	Nuclear	50	24.86	7.27	1.52	0.61	NS
	Joint	50	23.94	7.91			

On the above given data it was quite evident that the obtained value of 't' ratio was 0.61 and less than table value which is 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the 't' ratio could not be significant. So the null hypothesis Ho₂ could not be rejected and it was concluded

that there was no significant difference between students belonging from nuclear and joint family on their emotional stability.

Analysis of Emotional Progression of Students in Relation to Gender Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the Emotional Progression of students in relation to gender variation. For this the null hypothesis H_{03} was formulated as follows, “There will be no significant difference in the emotional progression of students in relation to gender variation”. For the appropriateness of the study and in order to test the differences in emotional progression the ‘t’ ratio was calculated as shown in the following table.

Table 5: Test of significance of difference on Emotional Progression of students due to Gender variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	‘t’	Remark
Gender	Boy	50	23.12	7.28	1.54	1.45	NS
	Girl	50	25.36	8.12			

On the above given data it was quite evident that the obtained value of ‘t’ ratio was 1.45 and less than table value which is 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the ‘t’ ratio could not be significant. So the null hypothesis H_{02} could not be rejected and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between boy and girl students in their emotion progression.

Analysis of Emotional Progression of Students in Relation to type of family Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the Emotional Progression of students in relation to type of family variation. For this the null hypothesis H_{04} was formulated as follows, “there will be no significant difference in the emotional progression of students in relation to type of family variation”. For the appropriateness of the study and in order to test the type of family differences in emotional progression ‘t’ ratio was calculated as shown in the following table.

Table 6: Test of significance of difference on Emotional Progression of students due to type of family variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	't'	Remark
Type of family	Nuclear	50	25.08	8.22	1.54	1.09	NS
	Joint	50	23.4	7.23			

On the above given data it was quite evident that the obtained value of 't' ratio was 1.09 and less than table value which is 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the 't' ratio could not be significant. So the null hypothesis H_{04} could not be rejected and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between students in their emotion progression due to difference in type of family.

Analysis of Social Adjustment of Students in Relation to Gender Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the Social Adjustment of students in relation to gender variation. For this the null hypothesis H_{05} There will be no significant difference in the social adjustment of students in relation to gender variation. For the appropriateness of the study and in order to test the differences in social adjustment the 't' ratio was calculated as shown in the following table.

Table 7: Test of significance of difference on Social Adjustment of students due to Gender variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	't'	Remark
Gender	Boy	50	22.92	7.50	1.44	0.40	NS
	Girl	50	23.5	6.84			

On the above given data it was quite evident that the obtained value of 't' ratio was 0.40 and less than table value which is 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the 't'

ratio (0.04) could not be significant. So the null hypothesis H_{05} could not be rejected and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between boy and girl students in their social adjustment.

Analysis of Social Adjustment of Students in Relation to type of family Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the social adjustment of students in relation to type of family variation. For this the null hypothesis H_{06} There will be no significant difference in the social adjustment of students in relation to type of family variation. For the appropriateness of the study and in order to test the type of family differences in social adjustment, 't' ratio was calculated as shown in the following table.

Table 8: Test of significance of difference on Social Adjustment of students due to type of family variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	't'	Remark
Type of Family	Nuclear	50	24.78	7.42	1.40	2.24	S
	Joint	50	21.64	6.56			

On the above given data it was quite evident that the obtained value of 't' ratio was 2.24 which was greater than table value which is 1.98 at 0.05 level but lesser than 2.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the 't' ratio (2.24) in case of type of family variation was significant at 0.05 level. So the null hypothesis H_{06} could be rejected and it was concluded that there was significant difference between students in their social adjustment due to difference in type of family. The result was in the conformity of the research conducted by Sharma (2012), Sinha (2014) and Mahmoudi (2012).

Analysis of Personality Integration of Students in Relation to Gender Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the Personality Integration of students in relation to gender variation. For this the null hypothesis H_{07} "There will be no significant difference in the

personality integration of students in relation to gender variation”. For the appropriateness of the study and in order to test the differences in social adjustment the ‘t’ ratio was calculated as shown in the following table.

Table 9: Test of significance of difference on Personality Integration of students due to Gender variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	‘t’	Remark
Gender	Boy	50	21.14	8.46	1.62	1.04	NS
	Girl	50	22.82	7.72			

On the above given data it was quite evident that the obtained value of ‘t’ ratio was 1.04 and less than table value which is 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the ‘t’ ratio (1.04) could not be significant. So the null hypothesis Ho₇ could not be rejected and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between boy and girl students in their personality integration.

Analysis of Personality Integration of Students in Relation to type of family Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the personality integration of students in relation to type of family variation. For this the null hypothesis Ho₈ There will be no significant difference in the personality integration of students in relation to type of family variation. For the appropriateness of the study and in order to test the type of family differences in social adjustment, ‘t’ ratio was calculated as shown below.

Table 10: Test of significance of difference on Personality Integration of students due to type of family variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	‘t’	Remark
	Nuclear	50	23.14	8.51			

Type of family	Joint	50	20.82	7.57	1.61	1.44	NS
----------------	-------	----	-------	------	------	------	----

On the above given data it was quite evident that the obtained value of ‘t’ ratio was 1.44 which was lesser than table value which is 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the ‘t’ ratio (1.44) in case of type of family variation was not significant. So the null hypothesis H_{08} could not be rejected and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between students in their personality integration due to difference in type of family.

Analysis of Independence of Students in Relation to Gender Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the Independence of students in relation to gender variation. For this the null hypothesis H_{09} “There will be no significant difference in the independence of students in relation to gender variation”. For the appropriateness of the study and in order to test the differences in social adjustment the ‘t’ ratio was calculated as shown below.

Table 11: Test of significance of difference on Independence of students due to Gender variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	‘t’	Remark
Gender	Boy	50	18.9	6.22	1.08	0.52	NS
	Girl	50	19.46	4.55			

On the above given data it was quite evident that the obtained value of ‘t’ ratio was 0.52 and less than table value which is 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the ‘t’ ratio (0.52) could not be significant. So the null hypothesis H_{09} could not be rejected and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between boy and girl students in their independence.

Analysis of Independence of Students in Relation to type of family Variation

One of the objectives of the study was to estimate the independence of students in relation to type of family variation. For this the null hypothesis H_{010} "There will be no significant difference in the independence of students in relation to type of family variation". For the appropriateness of the study and in order to test the type of family differences in independence, 't' ratio was calculated as shown in the following table.

Table 12: Test of significance of difference on Independence of students due to type of family variation

Variation	Sub Sample	N	M	SD	SE _D	't'	Remark
Type of family	Nuclear	50	18.66	5.19	1.08	0.96	NS
	Joint	50	19.7	5.67			

On the above given data it was quite evident that the obtained value of 't' ratio was 0.96 which was lesser than table value which is 1.98 at 0.05 level and 2.63 at 0.01 level of significance. Hence the 't' ratio (0.96) in case of type of family variation was not significant. So the null hypothesis H_{010} could not be rejected and it was concluded that there was no significant difference between students in their independence due to difference in type of family.

Findings of the study:

- From the result it was found that most of the students are emotionally immature. Findings also showed that there is no difference in emotional maturity in terms of gender variation.
- The distribution is normal distribution.
- Type of family variation also did not play any vital role in the emotional maturity of the students.
- Boys and Girls students belonging from different type of family did not influence the emotional stability of students.

-
- Boys and Girls students belonging from different type of family did not influence the emotional progression of students.
 - Gender variation did not play any vital role in case of social adjustment of students.
 - Type of family variation played a vital role in case of social adjustments of students.
 - Gender and type of family variation did not play any vital role in case of personality integration of students.
 - Gender and type of family variation did not play any vital role in case of independence of students.

Recommendations:

The present study highlights the level of emotional maturity among students across gender and type of family variation. It was found that majority of students are emotionally unstable and also girls are better emotionally than boys. The students must try to understand that what lies there which make them emotionally unstable. The levels of education don't make them emotionally mature. Emotional maturity is not something that grows with chronological age. Therefore, they must decide to have emotional maturity as a conscious choice and enjoy life in a happy and balanced way. Gender differences can be attributed to the variations in socialization process of both genders than to the inherent genetic character. Moreover, the difference is not so massive that it cannot be subdued. Therefore, the students must be provided opportunities to strengthen their emotions so that they can easily face the realities of life and make successful adjustments.

References:

Aashra, B. (2013). Emotional Maturity and Self-Actualization in Graduate and Post-Graduate Students, *Quest Journals Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*

- Jadhav, N. S. (2010).** *Relationship between home environment & emotional maturity of college going students of Belgaum District*, International Research Journal, October 2010, ISSN-0975-3486 RNI : RAJBIL 2009/30097 VOL I * ISSUE 13
- John Louis, R. and Doss, I. C. (2007).** Emotional Maturity of Post-Graduate Students in Pondicherry Region: Experiments in Education. Vol. XXXV, No.8
- Mahmoudi, A. (2012).** Emotional maturity and adjustment level of college students. *Education Research Journal* Vol. 2(1): 18 -19, Available online at <http://www.resjournals.com/ERJ>
- Sharma, B. (2012).** Adjustment and Emotional Maturity among First Year College Students, *Pakistan Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, Vol. 10, No 2, 32-37
- Sinha, V. (2014).** A Study of Emotional Maturity and Adjustment of College Students, *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, Volume: 4, Issue 5, ISSN - 2249-555X
- Sivakumar, R. (2010).** “A study on attitude towards democracy in relation to social and Emotional maturity”, Ph.D, Thesis, Annamalai University.
- Subbarayan, K. (2011).** A Study on Emotional Maturity of College Students, *Recent Research in Science and Technology*, 3(1): 153-155 Volume1 ~ Issue 4 pp: 15-18, ISSN (Online):2321-9467